

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES THAT DEVELOP STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES IN "MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY" LESSONS OF THE PRIMARY GRADE.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada, bugungi kundagi pedagogik texnologiyalarining ahamiyati, "ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi" darslaridagi kreativ metodlar, interfaol metodlar haqida bilib olishingiz mumkin.

Abstract: In this article, the importance of today's pedagogical technologies, "mother tongue and reading-literacy". you can learn about creative methods, interactive methods in the classes.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается значение современных педагогических технологий; «Родной язык и грамотность».узнать о творческих методах, интерактивных методах на занятиях

Kalit so'zlar: Kreativlik, pedagogik texnologiyalar, ijodiy fikrlash , yangiliklar, g'oyalar, interfaol metodlar.

Keys words:Creativity, pedagogical technologies, creative thinking; news, ideas, interactive methods.

Ключевые слова: Творчество, педагогические технологии, творческое мышление, инновации, идеи, интерактивные методы.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "It is necessary to form students' free and creative thinking, teamwork and communication skills. At the same time, it is necessary for us to expand support for talented young people, for our children to thoroughly master their mother tongue and foreign languages from school and learn to work on a computer".[1] Using computers and information technologies, new opportunities are created in the field of education, in educational activities and in the development of students' creative thinking. Information technologies allow to harmonize education with life in the process of implementation. Also, to further improve the field of pedagogical education, have the skills to apply modern knowledge and pedagogical technologies, and make a significant contribution to the socio-economic development of our

country. it is necessary to supply professional pedagogic personnel and introduce advanced educational technologies in the field for the training of qualified specialists.[2] Currently, the number of pedagogical personnel is increasing, which indicates that education is developing day by day. Why is it time to study educational technologies? The reason is that as the number of personnel increases, the competition becomes stronger. Therefore, people who are engaged in raising and teaching children and young people, who have special training in this field, should first of all have educational technologies. Educational technologies, pedagogical conditions may depend on the purposefully created creative educational environment in the classroom; the existence of a model of the teacher's creative behavior; subjective role in creative activity; maintaining a creative environment and creating situations of success. The most effective development of students' creativity is provided by purposeful, comprehensive pedagogical influence in the conditions of a continuous system of creative education. Creative pedagogy, as a field of fundamental practical pedagogy, should deal with the development of these and other issues. Also, it is to train potential specialists who think outside the box, are calm in difficult situations, and have a multi-faceted approach to finding a solution to the problem.[4] This process increases the responsibility of teachers. To what extent should we raise the status of pedagogic personnel? What is pedagogical technology? How and where can we use it effectively? In order to answer such questions, we must first study the teaching process, the teacher's and student's activities in it. The lesson is the cooperative, effective work of the teacher and the student. Positive organization of the lesson, effective use of time, correct choice of lesson goals, ability to use methods in their place, establishing cooperation with students and creating a positive-emotional atmosphere in the classroom are the teacher's is the main activity. To teach students to read, to help students acquire knowledge independently and to achieve a positive result in the lesson, in combination with various methods, the ability to understand and apply modern pedagogical technologies requires skill from the pedagogue. The content of the educational process consists of three parts.

- motivation;
- cognitive activity;
- management activity.

If these three components work together, it is possible to achieve a result in pedagogical technology. Trainings conducted on the basis of pedagogical technology satisfy the desire of students to express their attitudes to important life achievements and problems, and provide them

with an opportunity to think and justify their points of view. Also, the place and importance of innovative methods in the application of pedagogical technologies is great. The main goal of interactive methods is to encourage students to take active action, to involve them in the lesson, to teach them to work cooperatively.[2] For example, in the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy, the "brainstorming" method is used to ensure the students' activity during the training process, to encourage them to think freely and to free them from the inertia of the same thinking, to create colorful ideas on a specific topic. collects ideas, and also serves to teach to overcome the thoughts that appeared at the initial stage of the process of solving creative tasks.[5] In addition, after reading fairy tales on various topics, questions and tasks were introduced to encourage critical, logical and creative thinking. They are as follows: given a short story, various methods were used based on its content.

Silkworm (Fairy Tale)

The silkworm was envious of the beautiful butterfly that was flying from flower to flower. Because it could not fly like them. But it was good at spinning the cocoon. Therefore, it continued to spin the cocoon with enthusiasm. Finally, after spinning the cocoon, it fell into a deep sleep. After waking up, he broke the cocoon and went out. Then, he was very happy to see that the worm had turned into a beautiful butterfly and flew across the flower garden.

1. Find and write the spelling mistakes in the given words.

Butterfly, cocoon, silk, pleasure, for, sleep Children learn spelling rules and writing skills more perfectly through this.

2. Picture test.

What did the worm become?

3. Find words with the same consonants that appear next to each other in the text and write them down.

4. Listen to the audio and ask the following questions to check the students' understanding of the text. Acknowledging any reasonable response from a student makes the student feel engaged and valued, and encourages more creative thinking in the classroom.

1. Why did the silkworm lust after the butterfly?
2. How was the silkworm rewarded for his work?
3. What is obtained from the cocoon?
4. What does the silkworm feed on? [6].

Nowadays, interactive methods are being used in the teaching process in all educational institutions. This helps to fully understand the essence of pedagogical processes organized on the basis of interactive education and to ensure that they are effective, interesting, and of high quality. Lessons in interactive methods encourage the student to think creatively, to actively solve the received information, to express his opinion freely, to take the initiative, to find solutions to problems in groups, to work in cooperation, to express his opinion in writing.[7] The success of all the above methods depends on the questions and tasks given by the teacher. Using the cognitive activity of a young student with the questions encountered along the way does not give the expected result. In recent years, it is necessary to use modern pedagogical technology methods along with traditional methods in the educational system.[8] Through such methods, it is important for students to develop free, creative and creative thinking, follow spelling rules, and search for news. Elementary school students learn conscious reading and literate writing in their mother tongue classes, learn the rules of oral and written speech. Skills in the field of mother tongue (speech, reading and writing skills) are a necessary condition and means of students' educational work. In addition to acquiring reading skills, the student should first of all learn his native language, because the native language is the key to knowledge and intelligence.[9] The mother tongue is also a means of teaching other subjects: both social history and natural sciences are taught using the mother tongue. Therefore, the mother tongue plays a special role in the general development of the child and in awakening the desire for knowledge and work, skills are formed. Improving native language and reading literacy helps students practice listening, reading, speaking and writing skills, as well as grammar rules, in specific contexts. In fact, teaching students to think creatively from a young age lays the groundwork for them to achieve great things in the future. They will have useful information about the development of creative thinking skills and how accepting life's problems as opportunities rather than obstacles can help people get rid of depression. We should support the child in every way

from the moment he is born. It is also necessary to direct students to independent thinking, creative thinking, and innovation from the primary grade. Prospective tasks implemented in the field of education, with their relevance and practical importance, do not lag behind reforms in other fields. Because it is the need of the hour to continue the reforms in this field on a wider scale.

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